
Supplementary materials

Data for action in COVID-19 response: effectiveness of upscaling mitigation measures on the basis of weekly quantitative rapid risk assessments in Italy

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How the risk assessment tool works

The Italian risk assessment system is based on three pillars:

- **probability**, i.e. evidence of increased transmission as a proxy of increasing probability of uncontrolled SARS-CoV-2 spread in a region/AP,
- **impact**, i.e. evidence of an unsustainable pressure of COVID-19 on hospital services, and
- **resilience**, i.e. the capacity of the public health system to withstand the burden of the pandemic and maintain its functions within the “test, track and trace” strategy to contain SARS-CoV-2 transmission.

Three sets of quantitative indicators were used to assess these pillars where the first set (“data quality” output indicators) defines the minimum data completeness levels to allow the risk assessment; the second set (“resilience” output indicators) monitors the resilience of public health services in maintaining high levels of testing and contact tracing; the third set monitors the probability of SARS-CoV-2 uncontrolled spread and of an unsustainable impact of COVID-19 on hospital services (“probability and impact” result indicators). For each indicator, thresholds for alerts were defined.

As shown in Figure 1, Probability and impact were assessed separately using dedicated algorithms. The final question of each algorithm is a qualitative question allowing regional authorities to declare respectively an uncontrolled SARS-CoV-2 transmission that could not be managed locally and the presence of clusters in vulnerable settings such as hospitals and long-term care facilities.

Figure 1. Probability and Impact algorithms with risk matrix

Data sources, data quality and validation process

The described quantitative indicators were collated from the following existing surveillance systems:

- the aggregated surveillance system of SARS-CoV-2 cases coordinated by the Italian Ministry of Health -MoH (providing more timely but less detailed data),
- the case based integrated microbiological and epidemiological surveillance system of SARS-CoV-2 coordinated by the Istituto Superiore di Sanità - ISS (previously described [1, 2])
- the COVID-19 hospital occupation rates monitor coordinated by the MoH.

In addition, a dedicated weekly reporting was set up specifically to capture the resilience and the qualitative indicators from existing subnational data-flows. Data collection for qualitative questions was also supported by the Italian Network of Epidemic Intelligence coordinated by ISS using a previously described methodology [3] and validated by regional health authorities.

All systems operate using digital platforms. The risk assessment team coordinating the collation of data comprised experts from the ISS and the MoH already engaged in the described surveillance activities. Therefore, all data flows needed were embedded in existing systems. The data suppliers were 21 official Public Health Regional focal points each nominated by an Italian Region/Autonomous Province (AP).

Each of the existing systems described is regulated by technical documents that define data quality requirements and include data quality verification processes [2]. For risk monitoring, therefore, data quality requirements were simple (Table 1 – main manuscript). If data completeness was below any of the defined thresholds during a monitoring week in a Region/AP, the risk assessment was not considered feasible. A non-feasible risk assessment equalled to a high-risk assessment. The reason for this is that during an emergency the quality of data typically decreases as the health system struggles to maintain surveillance activities. We therefore considered, on a precautionary basis, the absence of data as a signal of health system stress.

Data was analysed by weeks from Monday to Sunday. At the beginning of each week, the Regions/APs verified the data they had collected and reported during the previous week (i.e. reporting week). The ISS downloaded the consolidated version of the data, typically by mid-week, and reported back on the same day to each Region/AP the calculated indicators, asking for any feedback including corrections by the following day. The national risk assessment report was usually completed the next day and discussed by a steering committee (called “*cabina di regia*”) coordinated by the MoH and composed of 9 experts from the MoH, Regions/APs and the ISS. The final report was published online each week [4] and used by decision makers. This validation process supported regional focal points in reporting timely and correct data. This process was consistent across Regions/APs and throughout the study period.

As expected during an emergency, the quality of data tended to decrease, especially during high incidence weeks in which health services were under extraordinary stress. The described efforts made to verify and validate data each week limited the risk of errors in the data used.

The rationale of adding resilience component of the risk assessment

The resilience pillar of the Italian Risk Assessment approach was innovative as it is not included in the original ECDC framework.

In particular, in the Italian tool, when multiple alerts from the resilience elements (“resilience” output indicators) occurred, the risk obtained through the combination of probability and impact was automatically up-scaled to the next risk level.

Risk assessment tools developed in an international context capture data typically through literature, epidemic intelligence and international surveillance. These in turn record case counts, hospitalizations and deaths but do not typically monitor indicators related to health system performance.

The natural history of COVID-19 leads to a two to four-week delay from case detection to hospitalization and death. This means that public health services signal critical challenges in testing, tracing, isolating cases weeks before hospitalizations and death rates increase. Likewise, due to the incubation and detection periods of the disease, once increased restrictions are in place a few weeks are needed to observe their full effect on case counts and longer time is required to see a decrease in the number of hospitalizations and deaths.

As Italy required a risk assessment tool able to detect, as early as possible, when the epidemic was exceeding the health system's capacity and new drastic containment measures might be needed, a health system resilience component was therefore considered crucial.

Probability and Impact assessments in the context of increasing immunization coverage in the Italian eligible population.

Between May 4th 2020 and September 24th 2021, the ISS performed 71 weekly risk assessments. Figure 2 shows the assessment of probability (A) and impact (B) by Region/AP between November 2nd, 2020 and September 24th, 2021. The first dotted line represents the start of the vaccination campaign (December 2020) and the second line the time in which vaccination coverage reached 50% among the Italian eligible population (July 2021).

While indicators of increased transmission (probability) continued being triggered also in more recent months, the impact of immunization is quite evident in the performance of impact indicators as high levels of impact on hospital services stopped being observed from the month of June 2021.

Figure 2. Weekly assessment of the probability (A) and impact (B) components of the risk assessment between November 2, 2020 and September 24, 2021. Dotted Lines represent the mean incidence. Darker and solid lines represent the start of the vaccination campaign (December 2020) and the time in which vaccination coverage reached 50% among the Italian eligible population (July 2021). In the figure the word «Region» is used to include both Italian Regions and Italian Autonomous Provinces.

Reliability of the risk assessment and added value of the resilience component

To evaluate the performance of the risk assessment system in supporting the escalation/de-escalation of restrictions, we calculated the incidence of ascertained severe (i.e., that would need hospitalization) and lethal infections (i.e., that would lead to death) during the week of the risk assessment and up to two weeks later.

We compared the temporal evolution of these indicators with and without interventions, where an intervention was defined as escalation in regional restrictions, as previously described [5], occurring either in the same week of the assessment or in the two previous ones.

We considered a benchmark event the beginning of the vaccination campaign in Italy that occurred on the 27th of December 2020 and have considered a buffer of 1 month prior to this date as a data cut-off criterion, taking into account that the analysis covers a two-weeks follow-up time and outcomes such as hospitalizations and death are notified with a delay of up to 1 month from infection in Italy [6].

This analysis was performed for two different time periods:

1. From the start of the risk assessment activity (week starting the 4th of May 2020) to the 27th of November 2020,
2. From the 28th of November 2020 to the 13th of September 2021.

Table 1 summarizes the occurrence of risk levels in the considered time periods (May 4-November 27, 2020 and November 28, 2020 – September 13, 2021) and the corresponding occurrence of interventions.

The level of risk assigned by the regional assessment system was found to be accurate in interpreting the short-term evolution of the epidemiological situation when no additional interventions were put in place in a time-frame of three weeks. As shown in Figure 3 and 4 (for each time period considered), in both periods the incidence of severe (upper row) and lethal (lower row) infections over time is shown. The dotted lines represent data from Regions/AP in which escalation of regional measures took place in the same week of the assessment or in the two weeks before, solid lines show data from Regions/AP in which this escalation did not take place.

We found that in both study periods and in absence of interventions, an assessment of low risk in a Region/AP was not followed by a major increase of disease burden in the following three weeks; an assessment of moderate risk was followed by a moderate incidence growth, a moderate/high risk (i.e., “moderate with high probability of progression to high” – see subsequent paragraph) resulted in a brisk epidemiological worsening, and high risks always occurred with an already high incidence of severe and lethal incidence, which further rose but not as briskly, likely due to saturation effects and possibly individual behaviour changes also in absence of interventions. This data shows the overall robustness in the risk assessments performed both in the pre-vaccination period and in more recent months.

Table 1. Assigned risk level and implemented escalation of interventions across the 21 Italian regions and autonomous provinces. Moderate/High stands for “Moderate risk with high probability of progression to high risk”.

Period		Low	Moderate	Moderate/High	High	Resilience alert
May 4-Nov 27, 2020	Assigned risk level in assessments	255	229	44	48	33
	Occurrence of an escalation in regional restrictions in same or previous two weeks	0 (0%)	13 (6%)	35 (80%)	48 (100%)	30 (91%)
Nov 28, 2020 – Sep 13, 2021	Assigned risk level in assessments	291	276	91	81	17
	Occurrence of an escalation in regional restrictions in same or previous two weeks	136 (47%)	13 (54%)	72 (79%)	65 (80%)	14 (82%)

Despite a low number of occurrences (n=3 in both study periods in absence of interventions, see Table 1), when a resilience alert led to a high risk assessment, this tended to be followed by a very rapid growth of severe and lethal cases.

When an escalation of interventions had taken place during the week of the assessment or in the previous two, the incidence of severe and lethal infections increased less dramatically or decreased over the two weeks following the assessment itself. For any given risk assessment, interventions tended to be started when the incidence of severe and lethal infections was comparatively higher.

Figure 3. Weekly incidence of infections leading to hospitalization (top row) and to death (bottom row) for different levels of risk (Low, Moderate, Moderate with likelihood of progression to high, High; Resilience alerts) assessed between May 4, 2020 and November 27, 2020. Lines represent the mean incidence. Darker and solid lines represent assessments for which escalation of restrictions did not take place in the same week of the assessment or in the two weeks before (see Table 1 for sample size for each risk level and intervention category). In this period, for high risk no dark solid lines are present as in all cases escalation of restrictions took place.

Figure 4. Weekly incidence of infections leading to hospitalization (top row) and to death (bottom row) for different levels of risk (Low, Moderate, Moderate with likelihood of progression to high, High; Resilience alerts) assessed between November 28, 2020 and September 13, 2020. Lines represent the mean incidence. Darker and solid lines represent assessments for which escalation of restrictions did not take place in the same week of the assessment or in the two weeks before (see Table 1 for sample size for each risk level and intervention category).

The additional information provided by using projections of hospital bed occupancy

On October 9th, 2020, based on the risk assessment for the week ranging from the 28th of September to the 4th of October 2020, the “cabina di regia” concluded that the epidemic was once again in an acute phase. At that time most Regions/APs were classified at moderate risk of an uncontrolled and unsustainable outbreak. High risk was not reached due to the fact that occupancy rates in medical and intensive care units (ICUs), while rapidly increasing, were still below the alert thresholds (indicators 3.8 and 3.9 in Table 1 – main manuscript).

In order to identify those Regions/APs in which the impact of COVID-19 on hospital services was expected to rapidly increase above alert levels, from the following week we started calculating the probability of breaching the occupancy rate alert thresholds in non-intensive wards (40% of available beds) and ICUs (30% of available beds) if the observed reproduction numbers (R_t) were maintained constant within the following 30 days. Regions classified at moderate risk but having a probability above 50% of breaching these thresholds in the following month, were since then classified as “moderate with a high probability of progression to high risk” (defined in Figures 3 and 4 as “Moderate/High”).

We used the renewal equation [7] to project the expected number of new symptomatic cases $C(t)$, under the assumption that the reproduction number would remain constant throughout the projection period, and equal to the latest available estimate obtained from the curve of hospitalized cases. We obtained the projected number of new admissions over time, $h(t)$, by assuming that a fraction p of all symptomatic cases are admitted after a delay from symptom onset (sampled from the observed distribution) [8]. We obtained the projected number of discharges over time, $q(t)$, either due to recovery or death, by assuming that newly admitted patients are discharged after a delay from admission (sampled from the observed distribution of patient length of stay) [8]. Finally, the projected bed occupancy, parametric with p , was computed as:

$$B(t; p) = p \cdot \sum_{\tau=0}^t (h(\tau) - q(\tau))$$

Parameter p was estimated for each region and date by matching the value of $B(t)$ with the latest available occupation data, to account for differences across regions and over time in the ascertainment rates of symptomatic cases and patient management criteria. The procedure was repeated separately for non-intensive hospital wards and for ICUs.

The method for projecting the hospital bed occupancy was sufficiently accurate within 15 days if no significant epidemiological changes (e.g., due to changes in contact restrictions) occurred after projections, so that the assumption of a constant reproduction number was verified (Figure 5.A-B). Conversely, when restriction levels were increased after the projection date, for example following the implementation of a regional restriction system on November 6, 2020 [11], projections systematically overestimated the bed occupancy (Figure 5.C-D).

Figure 5. Projected bed occupancy in non-intensive hospital wards and in intensive care units in Italy. Panels A and B show projections computed on September 15, 2020, in absence of successive control interventions. Panels C and D show projections computed on November 5, 2020, just before the application of a regional-based system of restrictions on November 6. Lines: median projections; dashed areas: 95% prediction interval; black dots: data used for calibration; coloured dots: observations unknown at the date of projection.

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